

Research

Client Satisfaction Regarding Services Under Medical Tourism

Arafat Habib¹, ANM Shamsul Islam², Mohammad Farhadul Haque³, Emily Akter⁴, Md Mahmudul Hasan⁵ *

¹Medical Officer, Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS), Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Associate Professor, Department of Public Health and Hospital Administration, National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), Dhaka, Bangladesh

³Assistant Director, Shaheed Monsur Ali Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology and Venerology, Enam Medical College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

⁵Consultant, Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Amar Hospital Ltd, Dhaka, Bangladesh

***Corresponding author:**

octemon87@gmail.com

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Abstract: As a result of healthcare globalization, Asian countries such as Thailand, Singapore, India and Malaysia export healthcare services and became popular medical tourist destination for patients from Bangladesh. While other countries benefit from medical tourism, Bangladesh is not only lagging behind but also losing patients to these countries. The present study aimed to find out the level of client satisfaction among the outbound patients of Bangladesh. A cross-sectional study was conducted among conveniently selected 133 respondents in visa centers of India, Thailand, Singapore and Malaysia in Dhaka city. Data were collected from the respondents using a semi-structured questionnaire through a face to face interview. Nearly half (56.4%) of the respondents were from the age group 45 to 59 years while the age range was 18 to 69. Two third (74.4%) of the respondents were male and the rest of them were female; among them 33.8% were graduated from university. About 88% of the respondents were from the Indian visa application center. None was there for seeking medical visas abroad the first time. All (100%) respondents gave positive opinion about the availability of Doctors, behavior of Doctors, the adequate time spent by Doctors, and Doctors' briefing pertaining to diseases. 97% of the respondents were satisfied about the quality of diagnostic centers abroad. 94.7%, 85.7% and 94% were satisfied about the hospital hygienic condition, waste management and hospital staff behavior; respectively. This study explored how Bangladeshi patients receive medical care abroad and was tried to provide suggestions in order to draw medical tourists from neighboring countries while maintaining our patients' health care services. By reducing the number of patients traveling for medical purposes, the loss of foreign exchange from the economy can also be prevented in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Medical tourism, Health care services, Customer satisfaction

Introduction

Tourism can be seen as a significant factor for each country's economic dynamism and sustainable development. In many countries, this industry is recognized as the primary source of income, employment, private sector growth and infrastructure development. There are many sectors attracting tourists. Of these, medical tourism is an individual's structured and systematic journey from one environment to another in order to recover physical and mental health. In recent decades, this branch of tourism has developed significantly. One of the medical tourism's main objectives is to travel for diagnosis, and physical and psychological rehabilitation. In addition to health care services, recreational activities are also often added to the ill health bundle. Patients prefer to receive services in other places due to the differences in the level of cities and countries on one hand, and the health services prices and the provided facilities level on the other hand.

According to the World Health Organization, the health care services and access did not equally and fairly split between and within nations across the world in spite of making significant investment in the medical and sanitary sector. On the other hand, less border hassle and increase air, road, and railway transportation facilities among countries has made travelling from country to country accessible and fast. As a result, people seek their need-based medical services beyond the border nowadays. Because of rising medical trips, demands for providing adequate and efficient services are increased in host countries as well.

Globalization of healthcare is benefiting many Asian countries as exporters of such services, for instance, Thailand, Singapore, India and Malaysia. Usually, these countries' health care services are popular among their neighboring terrains. Among them, Bangladeshi health care seekers are significant. It is estimated that Bangladesh spends \$2.04 billion per year on healthcare abroad and the figure is 1.94 per cent of the total GDP of the country [1]. A report states that India experienced about 460,000 foreigner patients at its various hospitals in fiscal year 2015-16 where 165,000 were from Bangladesh and this number was almost double compared to the previous fiscal year [2]. On the other hand, according to the Tourism Authority of Thailand, some 60,000 Bangladeshis went to Thailand for medical tourism in 2013 which was 11.89 percent higher compared to the previous year [3]. Considering the above statistics, it is clear that a great number of Bangladeshi patients visit foreign hospitals every year.

There are several reasons for visiting foreign countries in order to receive medical services. Of these, five principal factors are i) good quality of medical care, ii) experienced doctors and physicians, quality of nursing care (pre- and post-surgery) (iii) affordable low cost of surgery, (iv) non-availability of treatment in the home country and (v) modern/state of the art medical treatment and medical facilities in a foreign country [4]. All types of patients do not seek medical treatment for all diseases from abroad. The patients from Oman usually travel Thailand and India for receiving treatment related to orthopedic diseases [5]. In contrast, Bangladeshi patients visiting Indian Hospitals for acute to severe diseases related to orthopedic, eye, dental, brain, heart, stomach, kidney, liver, and spleen [4]. Along with the healthcare-related factors, socio-demographic status, geographical context, distance, cost of travel, accommodation, medical professionalism, hospital management and hospital staff behavior may also play significant roles in choosing a destination for seeking health care facilities.

Health care is one type of service, involving intangibility, heterogeneity and deep customer involvement. Customer satisfaction is recognized as one of the main health care outcomes and is directly related to the use of health services. Marketing researchers put forward various definitions of the idea of satisfaction. Customer satisfaction as the degree to which a company's actual performance meets the standards of its customers. Satisfaction is not a fixed definition but it is clearly and actually satisfaction with a level of goals accomplished. With the advancement of technology, the traditional method of understanding disease and treatment has changed; outbound medical tourism offers patients the opportunity to access procedures that are not available or affordable in their home countries, thereby potentially relieving patients from suffering and saving lives in their home countries regionally and globally.

While other Southeast Asian countries benefit from medical tourism, Bangladesh is not only lagging behind but also losing patients to these countries. Bangladesh imports more than 35% of international patients and more than 50% of overall medical tourism income, making it India's largest contributor to health and medical tourism [6]. Bangladeshi patients are likely to go abroad for medical treatment due to the higher perceived quality of the service, despite the fact that the same treatment can be more cost-effectively obtained within the country. As a result of increased medical spending overseas, the country's financial resources are systematically diverted from the economy. Therefore, this study sought to assess the level of client satisfaction regarding services

under medical tourism among Bangladeshi patients for a better understanding of the situation of concerned authorities in order to plan and implement the interventions.

Materials and methods

This study employed a cross-sectional design which was assigned to 133 conveniently selected participants at the visa application centers in India, Thailand, Singapore and Malaysia in the Dhaka metropolis. This survey lasted for almost 1 year period from January to December 2019. The study included Bangladeshi nationals who were willing to travel abroad for medical care as patients or attendants, regardless of age, gender and medical history. Those who were reluctant to take part in the study were excluded. Data was extracted through a semi-structured questionnaire. To address the error in the questionnaires, the questionnaire was pre-examined from more than 30 respondents who had similar inclusion criteria like the study sample.

After the necessary modifications, data was collected through the face to face interview. Before every interview, both written and verbal consent was taken from the participants. In order to get the perfect answer and to reduce the complexity of data analysis, the questionnaire was translated and asked into Bengali. After completion of data collection, each question was checked thoroughly for consistency and completeness. Data were cleaned and edited before analysis. Distribution of continuous variable was checked for normality. Construction of new variables recoding of some variables were done as per the requirement of analysis. Data analysis initiated with descriptive analysis. For descriptive analysis, categorical data were presented as frequency and percentages (%) and discrete and continuous data were given as mean and standard deviation (SD).

Prior to the study, ethical clearance was taken from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), Dhaka, Bangladesh. In addition, necessary permission was taken from the authority of the study place and NIPSOM before starting the data collection procedure.

Results

Figure 1: Distribution of the respondents by country chosen for medical treatment (n=133)

Figure 1 illustrates the percentage of participants on the basis of their presence on the various countries' visa center. Approximately 88% participants were at India visa center and only 12% of them were at the Thailand visa center. No participants were found on any other countries' visa center except India and Thailand.

Figure 2: Distribution of the participants who had other purposes along with the medical services (n=133)

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the participants who had other purposes along with the medical services for visiting their intended country. Except medical services, about 10%, 7%, 6% and 1% participants went to visit relatives, travelling, shopping and do business to the host country, respectively.

	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-29	8	6.0
	30-44	35	26.3
	45-59	75	56.4
	60-69	15	11.3
	Mean±SD	47.68±9.907	
Gender	Male	99	74.4
	Female	34	25.6
Marital Status	Married	118	89
	Unmarried	14	10
	Widow	1	1
Religious status	Muslim	110	83
	Hindu	21	16
	Buddhist	2	1
Occupational Status	Business	63	47.37
	Service Holder	30	22.56
	Retired	23	17.29
	Student	10	7.52
	Day Labor	4	3.00
	Housewife	3	2.26
Educational Status	No formal education	4	3.0

	Primary education	11	8.3
	SSC	40	30.1
	HSC	22	16.5
	University graduate degree	45	33.8
	Master's degree	11	8.3
Family Income	>50,000	5	3.72
(Monthly)	50,001-80,000	101	76
	80,001-100,000	12	9
	<100,000	15	11.27

Table 1: Socio-demographic distribution of the participants (n=133)

Table 1 represents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. About 75 participants (56.4%) were belonging to the age group of 45-59, followed by 35 participants was in the 30-44 age group (26.3%), 15 respondents was in the 60-69 age group (11.3%), and 8 participants was in the 18-29 age group (6%). The Mean±SD of age was 47.68±9.907. Among the respondents, there were 99 (74.4%) males and 34 (25.6%) females. Approximately, 118 (89%) participants were married, and 14 (10%) and 1 (1%) were unmarried and widow, respectively. 110 (83%) participants were Muslims, on the other hand, 21 (16%) were Hindus and 2 (1%) were Buddhists. In regards to the occupational status, 63(47.37%) participants were involved with the business, and 30 (22.56%), 23(17.29%), 10(7.52%), 4 (3.00%), and 3(2.26%) respondents stated their occupation as service holder, retired, student, day labor and housewife, respectively. Only 11 (8.3%) of the participants had a master degree and 45 (33.8%) had a bachelor's degree. The rest of the participants' educational qualifications ranged from non-formal education to HSC level. About 11.27% of respondents had a monthly family income <100,000 Bangladeshi Taka while 76% of the participants had a monthly household income of 50,001-80,000 Bangladeshi Taka.

Figure 3: Percentage of the respondents by the number of visit for medical purposes in abroad (n=133)

Figure 3 shows how many times the participants decided to seek treatment abroad. It was found that 45.1% of the respondents traveled the most for the third time, and 1% of the respondents traveled for the sixth, seventh and 20th time.

Kind of medical help seeking abroad in destination country	Frequency	Percentage
Routine checkup	48	36.1
Diagnosis of disease	26	19.5
For better treatment	55	41.4
For organ transplant	4	3.0

Table 2: Distribution of participants according to the types of medical help seeking (n=133)

Table 2 presents the statistics of what kind of medical assistance the respondents sought to travel abroad. Almost 48 (36.1) participants wanted to travel for a routine check-up while 26 (19.5%) respondents had the intention of traveling for getting their disease diagnosed. Furthermore, 55 (41.4%) participants wanted to visit foreign country because of receiving better treatment. Only, 4(3%) participants wanted to travel because of organ transplant.

Medical Conditions	Frequency	Percentage
Certain infectious or parasitic diseases	1	.8
Neoplasms	5	3.8
Diseases of the blood or blood forming organs	2	1.5
Endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases	3	2.3
Sleep-wake disorders	1	.8
Diseases of the nervous system	2	1.5
Diseases of the visual system	12	9.0
Diseases of the ear or mastoid system	3	2.3
Diseases of the circulatory system	24	18.0
Diseases of the respiratory system	7	5.3
Diseases of the digestive system	16	12.0
Diseases of the skin	2	1.5
Diseases of the musculoskeletal system or connective tissue	23	17.3
Diseases of the genitourinary system	23	17.3
Conditions related to sexual health	7	5.3
Pregnancy, childbirth or puerperium	1	.8
Symptoms, signs or clinical findings not elsewhere classified	1	.8

Table 3: Distribution of opinions of the respondents regarding the disease for which they choose a foreign country for treatment (n=133)

Table 3 shows the percentage of participants on the basis of medical conditions for which they wanted to go for foreign medical services. Among all of the respondents, 18% went for diseases of the circulatory system, 17.3% respondents went for both the diseases of the musculoskeletal system or connective tissue and diseases of the genitourinary system, 12% respondents went for diseases of the digestive system, 9% respondents went for diseases of the visual system, 5.3% respondents went for diseases of the respiratory system and conditions related to sexual health, 3.8% went for neoplasm, 2.3% went for endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases and diseases of ear and mastoid system, 1.5% respondents went for diseases of the blood or blood

forming organs and diseases of the nervous system and diseases of the skin each, rest .8% respondents went for certain infectious or parasitic diseases and sleep-wake disorders and pregnancy, childbirth or puerperium and symptoms, signs or clinical findings not elsewhere classified each.

Reasons behind choosing that country		Frequency	Percentage
Due to low treatment cost	Yes	58	43.6
	No	75	56.4
Due to better diagnosis and treatment	Yes	118	88.7
	No	15	11.3
No confidence in health system of the host country	Yes	52	39.1
	No	81	60.9
Due to attitude of the service provider	Yes	30	22.6
	No	103	77.4
For maintaining social status	Yes	2	1.5
	No	131	98.5

Table 4: Reasons for choosing the country to travel in the name of medical tourism

Table 4 illustrates the percentage of participants based on the reasons for travelling abroad in the name of medical tourism. It was found that the highest number of respondents (88.7%) preferred to travel for better diagnosis and treatment in abroad, 43.6% respondents chose to travel in abroad for low treatment cost, 39.1% respondents chose to travel in abroad for no confidence in health system of host country, 22.6% respondents for attitude of the service provider and 1.5% respondents for maintaining social status.

Category	Frequency			Percentage		
	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	N/A	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	N/A
Opinion about Health care professionals and their services						
Numbers of specialists	133	0	-	100	0	-
Availability of doctors	133	0	-	100	0	-
Behavior of doctors	133	0	-	100	0	-
Doctors spending enough time	133	0	-	100	0	-
Doctors briefing diseases	133	0	-	100	0	-
Nursing care	102	-	31	76.7	-	23.3
Competency about Nurse	114	-	19	85.7	-	14.3
Diagnostic center	129	1	3	97	.8	2.2
Prescribed diagnostic test	130	3	-	97.7	2.3	-
Prescribed medicine	127	6	-	95.5	4.5	-

Table 5: Participants' opinion about Health care professionals and their services

Table 5 pictures the participants' opinion based on the abroad health-care professionals and their services. It was observed that all the participants (100%) were satisfied with specialist Doctors' number, Doctors' availability, and their behavior, allocating time and briefing on disease towards patients. In the case of nursing care and their competency, 102 (76.7%) and 114 (85.7%) participants were satisfied, respectively. On the other hand, 129 (97%) participants were satisfied with diagnostic center, 130 (97.7%), and 127 (95.5%) participants were satisfied about prescribed diagnostic test and medicine, respectively.

Category	Frequency			Percentage		
	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	N/A	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	N/A
Opinion about Hospital management and accommodation						
Hospital hygiene	126	7	-	94.7	5.3	-

Waste segregation of hospital	114	5	14	85.7	3.8	10.5
Friendly behavior of staff	125	8	-	94	6	-

Table 6: Participants opinion about hospital management and accommodation

Table 6 represents the participants' opinions based on abroad hospital management and accommodation. It was noticed that about 126 (94.7%), 114 (85.7%) and 125 (94%) participants were pleased with the hygiene, waste management and behavior of hospital staff.

Discussion

This cross-sectional study was conducted on the conveniently selected 133 participants presented on the visa centers of India and Thailand for getting a medical visa. This study sought to assess the consumer satisfaction regarding services under medical tourism among Bangladeshi patients for a better understanding of the situation of concerned authorities in order to plan and implement the interventions.

The current study found that the age group of 45-59 years was the highest among the participants seeking medical tourism. A similar finding for age was found in a cross-sectional survey conducted in 2014 based on Thailand's medical tourism database [7]. Usually people get affected with the disease as they get older and after a certain period of life, people's income and savings increase. These may be the reasons behind people aged 45-59 looking for medical tourism more than other age groups. In the case of gender, male participants were higher than female participants and married individuals were more likely to be participants than unmarried and widows in the current study. In a previous descriptive case study, males' percentage was more than female and in terms of marital status, married participants were more than single and other relationship status [8]. In Bangladesh, women receive less health care than men. Also, women are dependent on their male family members because of its patriarchal culture. Since couples help each other in every aspect of life, more married people among the participants were looking for medical visas than their competitors in this study.

The present study noticed that individuals with the occupation of business were higher in number to get a medical visa at the visa center than the other occupational status. Furthermore, only a

tiny portion of participants had no formal educational qualification while the rest of the participants had at least a recognized educational certificate which refers almost all the participants were literate. This finding upholds the study conducted by Chakraborty et al. (2016) that literate people have a tendency to travel abroad for medical tourism [9]. In terms of household income, the survey found that about 85% of the participants had a family income of 50,001-100,00BDTK and 11.27% had a family income over 100,000. An earlier survey showed that participants in their survey all earned a minimum of 50,000 to a maximum of 150,000 BDT a month. In addition, data on distribution of respondents according to occupation also showed that majority of them had financial security and good jobs that is they were government service holder, students, medical doctors, or self-employed business men [4]. The current and the former finding support the literatures that higher the family income greater is the propensity to travel for medical treatment across border.

A previous study in Bangladesh shows that distribution of patients according to their sickness or affected parts of the body in terms of disease [4]. It is clear that most of the participants who travelled from Bangladesh to India for medical treatment suffered from various complex health issues which required not only diagnostic, but also invasive surgeries such as: orthopedic, eye, dental, brain, heart, stomach, kidney, liver and spleen. Similarly, the present study found that participants with a variety of diseases were willing to travel abroad for routine checkups or getting their disease diagnosed or better treatment or organ transplants. Participants seeking treatment services for the circulatory system were the most numerous, followed by those with musculoskeletal system or connective tissue and genitourinary system disorders though. Further research is required to carry out in this regard.

The current study was looked at the reasons for which people wanted to visit abroad in the name of medical tourism. This study found that despite having expensive medical services abroad, better treatment, and confidence in the healthcare system of the host country were important reasons for the participants to receive medical services from abroad. Likewise, Choi et al. (2018) reported in their study that Korea every year imports a great number of Chinese patients in their country in the name of medical tourism because of providing modern medical treatment [10]. Another study which was conducted in Bangladesh reported that Bangladeshi patients visit to India in medical tourism because India provides good quality of medical care with experienced

and competent medical professionals in hospitals abundant with modern technology at an affordable cost [4]. In addition, it states that the Bangladesh health system does not have treatment for all diseases or disorders. Therefore, the concerned authorities are requested to plan and implement the programs related to providing modern medical services along with gaining patients' faith.

Customer satisfaction is very important for running, holding, and providing services. The current study found that all participants were 100% satisfied in the case of abroad hospital's specialist Doctors' number, Doctors' availability, and their behavior, allocating time and briefing on disease towards patients. In regards to the nurses' competency and care, the number of participants' was quite impressive in considering their satisfaction. Furthermore, participants were pleased with the Doctor prescription along with the hospital staff behavior, and its management. These factors may influence Bangladeshi patients visit abroad for seeking medical treatment. A study in India considered medical professionalism, quality and good hospital services, standard hospital management, and professional relationship with the patients and hospital staff as influencing factors for medical tourists [11]. Therefore, it is urged to take necessary steps in re-arranging Bangladeshi health-care system considering the above factors for satisfying the patients.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research showed that the highest number of respondents preferred to travel abroad for better diagnosis and treatment in respect of type or severity of disease in India. This study significantly found that highest number of the respondents having diseases of the circulatory system went for Medical tourism. Majority of the respondents travelled for several times agreed about the treatment cost, transportation cost, accommodation cost which was affordable by them. Study showed that all of the respondents gave positive opinion about numbers of specialists, availability of doctors, behavior of doctors, doctors spending enough time, doctors briefing diseases and found important contributing factors for out bound Medical tourism. In addition having sufficient modern hospital with advanced technology with lower cost also plays as a pull factor for Medical tourism. The policy makers should address these issues and work on its root cause to restore the quality of health care sector in Bangladesh. Three factors are basically

needed in order to carry out the applications of the health tourism efficiently and productively. The first of these factors; is the tourism facilities (climate, nature, history etc.). The other one is health service facilities (hospitals, personnel, technologic facilities, specialties, affordable prices, healing water etc.). The last one is the existence of the professional organizations that will meet the health tourism sector with the consumers. The harmony and management of the existence of these factors can bring the current potency to efficient use.

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Conflicts of Interest

None

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